

CHESS SETUP

The positive effects of the CHESS SETUP solution are starting to show!

Welcome to our 7th newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading and we take the opportunity to wish you all a merry Christmas and happy winter holidays!

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

7th CHESS SETUP Consortium meeting and SSEER Seminar in Sant Cugat, Barcelona

On the 15th and 16th of October of this year 2019, the 7th Consortium Meeting and Exploitation Strategy Seminar (ESS) were held in Sant Cugat, Barcelona (Spain). It was an opportunity for every CHESS SETUP project partner to effectively communicate to all the consortium about the advances done and next steps of the project. All the works conducted are advancing fastly and the 3 pilots are already installed and working! The first day the meeting ended with a site visit of Sant Cugat's pilot, and all the partners were able to see the implemented CHESS SETUP system totally working in the sport center, including the swimming pools. The second day the consortium celebrated the ESS. The European Union selected CHESS SETUP's project as an ideal one for completed and ongoing research projects in the field of energy. The seminar helped CHESS SETUP to exploit the results of its work in order to achieve the intended mid to long term impacts, specially with the Business Model part of the project.

CHESS SETUP pilots

Sant Cugat's sport centre (Spain)

In Sant Cugat's pilot, the construction phase ended and the hydraulic and electrical monitoring installation is done. The start-up phase is going on and the system is already generating energy (thermal and electric), storing thermal energy in the tank and heating the swimming pool. The monitoring software is starting to show its benefits, for example, energy and economy savings were around 2500 kWh and 115€ per day in October. As the system did not start working until September, it has not had a great amount of energy during the summer, and therefore the overall energy contribution until today is low. When we have the full-cycle summer-winter, we will be able to know the real operation benefits of the system.

Lavola's headquarters (Spain)

Based in Manlleu, Lavola's headquarters has experienced during the last year a significant reduction of energy costs and emissions, thanks to CHESS SETUP.

The system has been fully on service since the end of June 2019, and we can start to see the first positive effects of CHESS SETUP solution: the energy savings nearly reach 26%, and considering only the heating system there is a 42% savings.

Lavola pilot

Sant Cugat pilot

Corby's dwellings (England)

After the considerable delays previously reported, construction of the Corby pilot re-started in November 2018 and since then, a lot of advances have been made! The Earth Energy Bank has finally been completed for the first 10 homes, the photovoltaic panels have been fully installed on the first set of homes as well, and the heat pump installation is completed. The first homes will be inhabited in January 2020. Since then, actual system operation data will be available.

Corby pilot

Online & Offline

Our Twitter account keeps on getting more visibility

As we enter the final phase of the project, CHESS SETUP (CSU) has never been that popular online. More than 990 tweets have been written since the creation and the page, and we have gained more than 345 followers.

News about the project, articles in relation with the CSU solution and interesting events are shared almost everyday!

Website and LinkedIn page updated

The pilots' sections of the Website is regularly updated as the works continue. All the new documentation is also added to the Website: now you can find newly videos showing the 7th Meeting in Sant Cugat, new photos of the pilots and a new area with our Sister Projects: CHESS SETUP is related to other EU funded projects focusing on seeking energy efficiency and self-sufficiency in buildings. We cross-promote and disseminate our projects and actions together.

On a professional side, our LinkedIn page is also more visible with nearly 200 visitors and 45 followers during the last year.

CHESS SETUP 2nd WEBINAR

On Thursday 19th of December 2019, CHESS SETUP project organized and hosted a public webinar called "An innovative approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-Sufficiency in Buildings".

This webinar has allowed the attendees to learn about the CHESS SETUP solution, results and its approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-sufficiency in buildings. Then, ReLATED, SUNHORIZON and HYBUILD EU projects, as guest speakers, presented their projects and approaches. At the end, a very interesting Q/A debate part was held.

In conclusion, the webinar evaluations were very good and it allowed the participants to know more about the topic, and disseminate the projects around attendees from Europe (Spain, Germany, England, Italy, Netherlands, Albania, Poland...) as well as internationally, such as USA.

"The main challenge for Thermal Energy Storage is to give 100% self-sufficiency".

Arnau Alacázar Casta, Barcelona Ecologia, Project Leader of CHESS SETUP EU H2020 funded project

In the last months...

Exploitation Strategy Seminar (ESS)

On 16th of October, CHESS SETUP partners participated in an Exploitation Strategy Seminar (ESS) organized by SSERR (Support Services for Exploitation of Research Results). The ESS is an INSTRUMENT to support partners of a research project to give sharper consideration to the potential of project results and their exploitation routes. The seminar was very profitable and helped CHESS SETUP consortium to brainstorm on how the project should address exploitation opportunities, to identify non-technical factors which could cause risks and potential obstacles that the future results of the project would remain unexploited, and to enhance the team's awareness of intellectual property rights (IPRs).

CHESS SETUP will take into account all the learnings and recommendations for its exploitation phase and business model!

Coming next year...

EU Sustainable Energy Week

The Policy Conference is the biggest European conference dedicated to renewables and efficient energy use in Europe. Sessions organised by the European Commission and energy stakeholders focus on sustainable energy issues, debate new policy developments, best practices and sustainable energy ideas. The Policy Conference of EUSEW 2020 will take place from 23 to 25 June 2020 in Brussels.

#EUSEW2020 Awards are HERE! Is #sustainableenergy close to your heart? Could your actions be an inspiration to others? We want to recognise YOU! Apply for the EU Sustainable Energy Awards!

Submit your application until 27 January 2020!

Click [here](#) for more info.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

For more information about the project, you can find us on, - Our [website](#), - Our [Twitter](#) account @ChessSetup - Our [LinkedIn](#) page

Comparte via:

<http://www.chess-setup.net>